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Research Article

**NON-INVASIVE VALUATION OF ESOPHAGEAL VARICES
IN PATIENTS WITH LIVER CIRRHOSIS**Dr Muhammad Zulqarnain¹, Dr Sahrish Batool², Dr Sidra Shaheen³^{1,3}THQ Hospital Sahiwal District Sargodha²THQ Hospital Jaranwala, Faisalabad**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To study the effectiveness of 6 non-invasive methods in the evaluation of the presence of esophageal varices in chronic liver disease (CLD).

Design: A prospective study of patients with chronic liver disease to detect the presence or absence of esophageal varices using non-invasive tests.

Place and Duration: In the Gastroenterology Department of Services Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Methods: Consecutive patients with clinical and para-clinical criteria of CLD with no upper GIT bleeding at presentation or in their past history were included in this study.

Results: During the study 103 patients with CLD met the inclusion criteria and were enrolled in this study, 60 were men and 43 women. The age ranged from 16 to 81 years, with an average age of 42.69 ± 16.96 years. Of these 103 patients, 62 (59.95%) had esophageal varices, 36 (58%) were small and 26 (42%) were large. Sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV values of 6 examined paraclinical and biochemical variables were evaluated. The sensitivity and the specificity for spleen diameter was 79.7% and 33.3% respectively, for platelet count 26.6% and 87.2%, for P.V diameter 39% and 47.4%, for Rt. lobe diameter/albumin ratio 23.4% and 82%, for spleen diameter/platelet count ratio 37.5% and 74.4% and for AST/ALT ratio 53.1% and 51.3%.

Conclusion: No one of the studied non-invasive tests had high predictive value or high sensitivity or specificity for prediction of esophageal varices, consequently upper GIT endoscopy is still the gold standard way in the diagnosis and grading of esophageal varices.

Key words: esophageal varices, non-invasive tests, EPC, Pakistan

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INTRODUCTION:

Cirrhosis (LC) is the final step in the assessment of any chronic liver disease that causes fibrous tissue formation, irregularities in liver architecture, and the formation of nodules that interfere with liver function and cause portal hypertension. The three main complications of portal hypertension are possible rupture and bleeding, ascites and hypersplenism, and esophageal varices¹⁻². Esophageal varices develop against the background of increased portal pressure due to increased portal vascular resistance. The hypertensive portal vein is directed back to the heart, up to 90% of the portal flow from the portosystem collaterals, and decompresses, which causes these vessels to expand. These vessels are usually located in the gastroesophageal junction under the mucosa and in which they occur as varicose veins of the stomach and esophagus³⁻⁴. Esophageal varices are found in the initial diagnosis in approximately 50% of patients with cirrhosis and are more common in patients with advanced chronic liver disease (CLD), Child-Pugh Class C, compared to patients in Class A children. - Early cough (85% vs. 40%). When varicose veins are formed, they grow from small to large 5-12% per year and bleed 5-15% per year. The greatest risk of bleeding occurs in large varicose veins classified as more than 5 mm in diameter, and also depends on the severity of the liver disease and the presence of red spots assessed on the basis of the Child-Pugh score. Varicose veins in endoscopy. Therefore, these factors should also be considered when classifying 'high risk varicose veins'. Up to 25% of newly diagnosed varicose veins will develop varicose bleeding within 2 years⁵⁻⁶. The mortality rate per bleeding is around 10-20%, and the annual survival is only 63%. For this reason, EV detection in patients with cirrhosis is a strong recommendation in all consensus reports⁷⁻⁸.

Current guidelines are small varicose veins to evaluate screening in all patients with cirrhosis at the time of initial diagnosis, varicose veins without varicose veins (depending on the severity of the liver disease), and enlargement of varicose veins and the need for preventive treatment. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy remains the gold standard of detection, but this test does not limit because it is invasive, expensive and poorly accepted by patients. If esophageal varices could be predicted in a non-invasive manner, this would limit the study to the population considered most at risk and reduce the number of endoscopes required⁹⁻¹⁰. This screening test should be simple, fast, repeatable and cost-effective. Several studies evaluated possible non-invasive markers of esophageal varices in patients with cirrhosis. However, findings from previous studies are controversial, and their usefulness in clinical practice is uncertain. Various studies in the past have shown that independent

parameters such as platelet count, splenomegaly, advanced condition of the child, serum albumin and high portal vein diameter in ultrasound are useful for this purpose. Giannini *et al*. A suggested ratio of platelet count to spleen diameter ≤ 909 as a true non-invasive marker for the presence of esophageal varices. Such predictive factors may vary in different populations due to differences in the aetiology of liver cirrhosis, the severity and nutritional status of liver disease, as well as sensitivity and specificity differ significantly in different studies. There is no data on this topic in patients in Pakistan.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:**patients**

A sample of our study included patients with CLD prospectively collected from the Gastroenterology Department of Services Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Patients with active bleeding, acute liver failure, patients with portal vein thrombosis, focal changes in liver function and persons, who previously had endoscopic sclerosis, esophageal varicose ligation or splenectomy were excluded from the study. A total of 103 people diagnosed with CLD completed the necessary data and were included in this study. Diagnosis of chronic liver disease was based on standard laboratory and ultrasound data consistent with EPC, as well as over 6 months of history and physical examination. The history included detailed information on the duration of jaundice, ascites, oliguria, swelling of the feet, spiders, and gastrointestinal bleeding. The presence or absence of acid, splenomegaly and hepatic encephalopathy have been reported. CBC, LFT containing serum bilirubin, albumin / globulin ratio, transaminase and prothrombin time were estimated. The modified Child-Turcotte-Pugh (CTP) class was calculated for each patient. Special tests include HBsAg (hepatitis B surface antigen), anti-HCV antibodies, antinuclear antibodies and anti-mitochondria antibodies as well as slit lamp testing for selected patients, serum and iron ceruloplasmin tests. All patients underwent the same specialist's ultrasound examination using the upper abdomen (LOGIQ9), including spleen diameter, portal vein diameter, right liver lobe diameter and presence. acid. Using the device (PENTAX-EPK-5000), better GIT endoscopy was performed in a single endoscopic unit and the presence or absence of esophagus or gastric varices, classification of varicose veins and other endoscopic results were recorded. Esophageal varices are classified as small and large varicose veins according to the criteria proposed at the Baveno I consensus conference.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20.0 (SPSS Inc. Chicago, IL, USA).

Continuous variables are presented as mean values and standard deviation. Data were compared using a chi-square test. The diagnostic performance of our variables was assessed by sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value (NPV).

RESULTS:

A total of 103 more patients were examined, 60 were men (58.3%) and 43 women (41.7%). The age is between 16 and 81 years old. The mean age of patients was 42.69 ± 16.96 years (Table 1).

Table 1 Distribution of the cases according to the gender and the age

Age in years	Male		Fe nale		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Less than 20	11	18.3%	0	0.0%	11	10.7%
21-40	24	40.0%	17	39.5%	41	39.8%
41-60	14	23.3%	21	48.9%	35	33.9%
>60	11	18.3%	5	11.6%	16	15.5%
Total	60	100.0%	43	100.0%	103	100.0%

At the time of diagnosis, the etiology of cirrhosis was predetermined and mainly included viral causes in 30 cases (29.1%), 24 (23.3%) hepatitis C infection (HCV) and 6 cases (5.8%) was from hepatitis B (HBV). In non-viral etiology, primary biliary cirrhosis was detected in 75 (72.8%) and 2 (39.8%) autoimmune causes in 22 (21.4) autoimmune cases in 41 (39.8%) cases. The etiology is unknown in cases (1.9%), in one case haemochromatosis and in 9 cases (8.7%). There was no statistically significant difference in the etiology of the disease between patients with esophageal varices and patients without esophageal varices ($p = 0.128$). Clinical presentations, clinical and paraclinical variables, and correlation with the presence of esophageal varices in our patients are shown in Table 2. $p = 0.000$ in both, where male and infant EVs were found more often in class C than B and A.

Table 2 Clinical and para-clinical variables of the study sample in relation with E.V

Variable	Presence of esophageal varices		Total	p-value
	No	Yes		
	No. (%)	No. (%)		
Male/Female	15 (25)/26 (60.5%)	45 (75%)/17 (39.5%)	60 (100%)/43 (100)	0
Age	38 (18-65%)	52 (16-81%)	40 (16-81)	0.09
Ascites	9 (25%)	27 (75%)	36 (100)	0.025
Spleen bipolar diameter (mm)*	123 (70-170%)	130 (95-200%)	132 (70-200)	0.561
Child-Pugh score				
A	29 (63%)	17 (37%)	46 (100)	-
B	10 (25%)	29 (74.4%)	39 (100)	-
C	2 (11%)	16 (89%)	18 (100)	-
Epistaxis	21 (47.7%)	23 (52.3%)	44 (100)	0.165
Jaundice	24 (43.6%)	31 (56.4%)	55 (100)	0.395
L.L oedema	8 (24.2%)	25 (75.8%)	33 (100)	0.027
Spider navi	3 (23.1%)	10 (76.9%)	13 (100)	0.187
Flapping tremor	12 (48%)	13 (52%)	25 (100)	0.336
Itching	13 (44.8%)	16 (55.2%)	29 (100)	0.515
Fatigue	35 (40.2%)	52 (59.8%)	87 (100)	0.838
Hemoglobin (g/dl)*	13 (7.8-16%)	13 (7.5-17.5%)	13 (7.5-17.5)	0.142
S bilirubin (mg/dl)*	2.5 (7-27%)	1.5 (5-33%)	1.5 (5-33)	0.486
S albumin (g/dl)*	3.6 (2.5-4.2%)	3.6 (1.8-4.2%)	3.6 (1.8-4.2)	0.567

Platelet count (per μ l)	6 (27.3%)	16 (72.7%)	22 (100)	0.176
Splenomegaly>120mm	39 (42.9%)	52 (57.1%)	91 (100)	0.326
Portal vein diameter >14mm	7 (29.2%)	17 (70.8%)	24 (100)	0.208
Platelet count/ spleen diameter ratio<909	11 (31.4%)	24 (68.6%)	35 (100)	0.192
AST/ALT ratio>1.1	25 (41%)	36 (59%)	61 (100)	0.702
Rt lobe diameter/Albumin ratio>4.4	7 (35%)	13 (65%)	20 (100)	0.597
*Median (minimum-maximum)				

Of 103 patients studied, 62 (59.2%) had esophageal varices, 36 of them (58%) were small (grade I and II), and 26 (42%) were large (grade III and IV) (Table III) 3).

Table 3 Causes of CLD and relation to the presence of esophageal varices in both sexes

Etiology			Presence and grades of EV	Sex				Total	
				Male		Female			
				No	%	No	%	No	%
Viral	No	%	No varices	2	14.3%	7	43.8%	9	30.0%
	-	-	Grade I EV	2	14.3%	1	6.3%	3	10.0%
	-	-	Grade II EV	2	14.3%	4	25.0%	6	20.0%
HCH	22	21.4%	Grade III EV	8	57.1%	4	25.0%	12	40.0%
	-	-	Grade VI EV	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
HBV	6	5.8%	Total	14	100.0%	16	100.0%	30	100.0%
Non-viral	-	-	No varices	13	28.3%	19	70.4%	32	43.8%
AIH	22	21.4%	Grade I EV	8	17.4%	2	7.4%	10	13.7%
Khat induced	41	39.8%	Grade II EV	11	23.9%	6	22.2%	17	23.3%
PBC	2	1.9%	Grade III EV	13	28.3%	0	0.0%	13	17.8%
Others(hemo-chromatosis, Unknown)	10	9.7%	Grade VI EV	1	2.2%	0	0.0%	1	1.4%
			Total	46	100.0%	27	100.0%	73	100.0%
Total	103	100.0%	-	60	100.0%	43	100.0%	103	100.0%

Sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of each of the 6 variables studied are shown in Table 4. The sensitivity range was from 23.4 to 79.7%, and the highest spleen diameter in the sensitivity test, the specificity range from 33.33% to 87.2%, and the highest specificity was observed in platelet counts, the PPV range was 64.2% - 77.3%, and the NPV range was 39.5% to 50% (Table 4).

Table 4 Sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV in our studied parameters

Parameter	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)
Spleen diameter	79.69%	33.33%	66.23%	50.00%
AST/ALT ratio	53.13%	51.28%	64.15%	40.00%
Rt. lobe diameter/Albumin ratio	23.44%	82.00%	68.18%	39.50%
PV diameter	39.00%	47.36%	71.43%	42.65%
Platelet count	26.56%	87.18%	77.27%	41.98%
SPRI	37.50%	74.35%	70.58%	42.00%

PPV=positive predictive value; NPV=negative predictive value; AST=aspartate transaminase; ALT=Alanine transaminase; PV=portal vein; SPRI=platelet count/spleen bipolar diameter ratio

DISCUSSION:

Esophageal varices are a dangerous clinical consequence of CLD. Since the detection of varicose veins causes a significant endoscopic load and costs, it is extremely clinically important to examine cheaper and non-invasive tools for correctly predicting esophageal varices. Promising predictive brands focused on typical laboratory variables such as platelet counts, LFT and albumin levels, and ultrasound parameters such as spleen and portal vein. We examined 103 cases, 60 (58.3%) are men and 43 (41.7%) are women¹¹⁻¹². The mean age of patients was 42.69 ± 16.96 years (Table 1). Causes of liver disease were not viral in 28 (27.2%) and non-viral in 75 (72.8%) cases. Of the viral etiologies in our study, HCV was responsible for most of them in 24 (23.3%) cases; Meanwhile, only 6 cases (5.8%) had HBV (Table 2). One explanation for these small cases of HBV and the main cases of HCV in our study may be that the Ibb Governorate in which this study was conducted had one of the highest rates of HCV infection prevalence. A country that can reach 4.2%. Meanwhile, the incidence in the capital, San, was 2.2%, and in Aden 0.6%. Another explanation may be the gradual decrease in HBV prevalence because HBV has been included in the vaccination program. Khat-induced hepatitis (autoimmune type) in 72.8% of non-viral causes, mainly 39.8%, autoimmune liver disease in 23.3% of cases, the case of hemochromatosis and its etiology in 9 cases (8.7%) are unknown (8.7%). Table 2) Chewing Khat is a very common social habit in Pakistan and East Africa due to its psychostimulant and euphoric effects. These effects are attributed to alkaloid compounds containing cathinone, and to a lesser extent noradrenaline. In recent literature and case reports, khat chew is blamed for the cause of severe non-viral AIH-like liver disease, but mainly because of its evolution, clinical and paraclinical features, and response to immunosuppressive therapy¹³.

In this study, 3 individual parameters and 3 composite parameters were evaluated. We measure sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV for each

parameter. No single parameter was found that offered a self-sufficient predictive function for esophageal varices. Also, the combination of many parameters (platelet count, spleen, lobe diameter, albumin, AST and ALT) did not significantly improve predictive accuracy in our patient's studied¹⁴. Several studies suggest that platelet count may predict the presence of EV in patients with liver cirrhosis. However, the threshold for separating the presence of varicose veins is from 68,000 to 160,000 / mm³. Sensitivity to thrombocytopenia ranges from 62% to 100%, and specificity from 18% to 77%. In our study, the specificity at the 100 x 106 cut-off point for platelet sensitivity was 26.56% and 87.18%, respectively. This wide range of sensitivity and specificity can be explained using different borderline points and different CLD etiologies in different studies. To improve the predictive value of platelets, it was combined with bipolar spleen diameter, but the platelet / spleen diameter ratio sensitivity was only about 37.5%, specificity 74.35%, PPV 70.58% and NPV 42%. These results are inconsistent with the preliminary results of the study in which Giannini et al., With the same limit value of 909, reported PPV at 96% and NPV at 100%. Unfortunately, despite the promising preliminary results of Giannini et al., The rate of platelet count / spleen diameter in our study was not a reliable tool for detecting esophageal varices¹⁵. The longitudinal diameter of the spleen had a sensitivity and specificity of 79.6% and 33.3%, respectively, which is not consistent with Homopolar et al. And Hassan et al. The lobe / albumin ratio was evaluated in one study involving 94 patients with cirrhosis.

CONCLUSION:

Non-invasive tests for predicting esophageal varices are not sensitive enough and / or specific enough to prevent detection of upper gastrointestinal endoscopy in CLD patients.

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